

Mohal novel by Youssef Zaidan: A Study of Vision and Formation

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Abstract

The first discusses the vision and the intellectual and social implications by discussing clear themes represent the idea of terrorism, as the protagonist "Muhammad" transformed in this novel from a stable and trustworthy figure to being imprisoned in Guantanamo Bay, the idea of love, wealth and control of money, and the idea of Jihad and the concept of Takfir and other implications that we will discuss in this research. As for the second axis: it discusses the artistic composition in this creative work by realizing the significance of the title, the chronological structure, the narrative character, the narrator's dominant voice in this novel and other artistic connotations that represent dramatic events of an artistic character, which is what distinguishes this work. This novel will not be read in isolation from its chronological and social context, as the role of (Zidane), who created these narrative vocabulary, is manifested within a series of units related to the factors of narrative juxtaposition, causal and temporal factors without neglecting the structures that make up the narrative discourse as an independent structure, and I mean here that the reference to the historical context for this work, it will not be received except to the extent that it is hidden in the folds of the narrative or recorded in it, and by referring to the social outward as a textual document that forms one of the common denominators between the writer and the recipient. Perhaps the novel "Mohal" has not received an independent study in its intellectual and artistic structure despite its importance, except in fragments scattered in cultural newspapers and magazines, including what was mentioned in the cultural attaché of An-Nahar newspaper by Sobhi Musa on 10/15/2018 and presented by the researcher in the Department of Arabic Language at the University of New Delhi "Muhammad Shafi'i" about Youssef Zidan and his trio "Mohal", "Guantanamo" and "Noor" (2). This prompted the researcher to single out an independent research on this novel, perhaps it would fulfill the desired purpose of this study and uncover an independent study of the importance of this novel on the level of vision and formation.

1. Introduction

This study reveals intellectual and social implications and themes of the Egyptian novelist "Youssef Zaidan" in his novel "Mahal", a novel that is clearly linked to the personality of this writer from many aspects, as it presents this young man's journey the "protagonist" from his home (Egypt) to other countries and places. Perhaps the title of this novel is in harmony with the multiplicity of places and bears within it the dramatic justification for travel.

Delving into the biography "Youssef Zaidan" makes us look closely at a problematic figure characterized with enlightening thoughts for the human acting in this world through mystical meanings that dominated the writer's poetic language. His specialization in Arabic manuscript heritage and his philosophical writings in the history of science and demanding human issues made him a largely encyclopedic writer.

Mohal is the first part of the "Zidane" trilogy, followed by "Guantanamo" and "Noor" (1). A trilogy in creative literature means a novel or story of three axes, each axis has a unit related to the general topic or dramatic content.

The novel "Mohal" does not present a biography or a historical document. Rather, we read a fictional artistic formation in which the real and the imagined are consistent. And the in-depth vision presented by "Youssef Zaidan" of the movement of existence and the reality of man represents a dramatic drive for the movement of his characters and heroes in this novel, which was based on the journey and the multiplicity of travels. Perhaps the semiotic title "Mohal" remained a place of ambiguity on the recipient as it guides him to multiple connotations that represent the impossibility, the multiplicity of places, the ability and empowerment. To be read in multiple ways: Mahal (places), Mohal (impossible), Mihal (power).

This is what prompted the writer intentionally to address it without diacritics to make the recipient search for his desired meaning in terms of significance and interpretation.

The intellectual and social implications of the novel "Mohal"

The theme of "Love": the woman, "the beloved", the mother-wife.

This theme is evident in textual spaces stretching across the pages of the novel and represents a psychological obsession for the protagonist "Muhammad", who fell in love with a university girl who came on a trip from her home "the city of Alexandria" where she studies sociology to the city of Aswan, where the hero "Muhammad" works, to get acquainted with this place and they start a love story full of dramatic transformations that overwhelmed the vocabulary of this novel.

Perhaps the woman in Zaidan's novel represents a precious icon that he presented in a positive way and referred to her role in life giving her best qualities, as he expressed this in a symbolism full of love and excitement for his hidden components in his confused self.

The protagonist of the novel "Mahal" a twenty years old man from the far south of Sudan, who came to work as a tour guide in the cities of Luxor and Aswan whose utmost dreams is marrying a Nubian girl who will compensate him for his moments of poverty and deprivation, and says: "If he had violated the veil now, he would have woken up from his delusions and stopped dreaming. Until the impossible hope of marrying a Nubian girl gains him, she will be a charming presence and loving, donor, like this lake, calm and tender." (3) The novel, p. 8

The doctrinal firm that our hero lived from his early childhood years, when he was brought up in a traditional family; The mother lives with his seven siblings in a spacious house in the Omdurman area on the banks of the Nile, opposite the capital Khartoum, and the father is a leather merchant who brings it to the merchants in Aswan.

He believes that the job of women is to stay at home to raise children, which he learned from his father in his early years, saying: "Four years ago, he finished his high school years, qualifying for university, and he had to work alongside his studies, to help his working father and thus rise to the status of men."

"If men imitate women and women imitate men, the resurrection will soon take place. Do not gain Haram no matter how hard you are hungry, for dying from starvation is easier than living by Haram, if you commit adultery, it will be done to your mother or sister, so what you do will be done to you, death with honor, better for you than living with shame." (4) The novel, p. 11

The researcher sees that the dialectic of freedom and commitment will seem overwhelming in our protagonist life during his distant travels. He expressed his childhood flashbacks in moments of recovery, through which he observed the place he was raised in, while Nile River represents a renewed symbolism in his life, and this is what started in its deep-rooted values.

His dreams for the near future seemed to be nothing more than regular dreams of a young man who would graduate university and live with his wife, who he wished for himself in a simple way that seemed naive at times. He says: "Next summer he gets a university degree and then returns from Sudan to Aswan to reside the rest of his life with his Nubian woman who will be- with God's permission- entrusted, and he will have many children from her." (5) The novel, p. 13

We are dealing with a character inhabited by the ideological firm, as we mentioned, as he rejects any relationship between man and woman outside the framework of marriage that God Almighty has permitted, here is the British tourist Christine wants him and offers a reward for that when the refusal came categorically, saying: "Two years later the official guide suddenly fell ill, and the delegate came to ask him to escort a wonderful English group to Philae temple, among them was a very shining well shaped girl, who could not bear the heat or the clothes, named Christine.

"She did not say anything, but her eyes were promising a lot if he approached.... She left her address and phone number with him and hoped that he will change his mind. He is not naive and his opinion will not change, and he will never deviate from his hope in Paradise ..." (6) the novel, p. 17

The sanctity of marriage, as this young man sees, came from religious source that he was raised and believed in, where he says: "Marriage is

Not only the most beautiful thing a young man can do, but his ultimate goal. He works to earn money with which to marry, and love a girl with all his senses, to marry her ..." (7) The novel, p. 25

the first shock of seeing the girl of his dreams, which was not in his current perspective, a brown girl coming from Alexandria with a tourist group that at first glance sees her an educated intellectual who attracted his attention from the first time in a way that contrasts with his classic view of the woman / beloved / wife that he depicted for us at the beginning of the pages of the novel.

Amidst the crowd, he turned accidentally, and saw a girl among them with a black suitcase attached to her shoulder, and in her right hand was a small book her palm hides its title, she was graceful, bare hair, rare features, neither eastern nor western. Her smooth skin is unattended brown, her long, profuse hair is black and strong, her wide eyes have a wonderful color mixed in gray and green, greeting him on her way to the bus ladder, saying "Hi" and respond without hesitation: Hi, with God mercy and blessings. " (8) The novel, p. 28

The descriptive pauses that the author intended intentionally portray to us clearly his vision of the woman he had always dreamed of in a different way. He says: "He saw her from afar as he was coming towards her, and she looked like the girls of Sudan and Aswan, because she wore black robes whose edges were framed by golden strings, and the mind was left with her calm and revered beauty He carried the air to his nose a charming fragrance as if it were jasmine ..." (9) the novel, p. 41

His vision of the educated woman represented by this girl called (Noor) is perhaps an ambitious vision that the writer wanted for an educated Arab woman in a way that contrasts with what he saw and lived by the rural and village women in southern Egypt and Sudan. He wished that the woman would transform from the image of the enslaved despised in her body by men to the image of a responsible liberation he wanted for her in the ambition of what he would face next (10) He was overjoyed when she told him that she was studying sociology, and he wanted to let her know that he was studying it, so he asked her the usual question among the students: Who is the founder and inventor of sociology, Ibn Khaldun or Auguste Comte? They laughed together and then talked with abundance and relish, on Auguste Comte, Emile Durkheim and Karl Marx ...) (11) The novel, p. 42

It is worth noting cultural references that "Youssef Zaidan" dealt with regarding the suffering of Egyptian and Arab women in his creative works and at the beginning of the trilogy Mohal."

"And this is what the researcher (WaelTawfik) sees in the Egyptian newspaper Al-Nabaa, announcing that the researcher and academic Youssef Zaidan insisted that he explore the depths of the female "Noor" heroine of the novel, which is of monodramatic type as its events take place in the orbit of one person who narrates the events through his own point of view and interact with other characters, there are no parallel stories that intersect or intertwine with the main line, but they are all strings branching out from and returning to the protagonist.

Women, according to Youssef Zaidan, face severe suffering, as they are captive to their social surroundings that shape them as they want, prey to the gaze and ambitions of men, and hostage to the will of their financial supporter.

This is what the researcher "Al Kaber Al Dadisi" sees in his article The Woman in Youssef Zaidan's Narrative Project. "The subject of women has formed a basic theme in the novel throughout its long history, a cause of war sometimes, and a way of happiness and the source of revelation and inspiration in others. Others made her sacred and goddess while some made her the status of decadence and impurity and the source of every vice ..." (13) Rai Al-Youm newspaper, 9/17/2014 Cultural Attaché.

"It is not possible to study the contemporary novel in the Arab world without examining one of the novelists who have profoundly distinguished vision and treatment of narration, a thinker of various types of knowledge, medicine, philosophy, mysticism, investigation, creativity..." (14) Al-Rai Al-Youm newspaper / 17 9/2014

His childish feeling came to the first moment of love that shook his tired heart from traveling, as time stood in an independent fictional unit that the creator made on his tongue dominant in the narrative narration foretells the overwhelming joy of this first love: "In his room, a smiling face stuck to his face as he looked at the ceiling sheets with joy the little ones on the night of Eid, he kept secretly recovering what he had heard tonight from her words, and retrieving her sociable smile, until he took a delicious sleep to the early morning ... and he walked to the hotel as if his legs had become two wings ..." (15) The novel, p. 43

Here, the narrator, the dominant "protagonist" who grasps the keys of the narration, surprises us with a painting filled with sadness and waits for the distant coming for a moment to end the trip of the students who were accompanied by a tourist guide, including his lost lover, to leave the place in the hope of a desired return.

"The trip met at six in preparation for the journey and the separation on the pavement. He helped everyone move the bags, and Noor did not need help, it was he who needed a sedative for his heartbeat. Her eyes blinked when they bid farewell to surrendered without promises or hope for a meeting, and how do they meet while she is heading north while he is being drawn to the south?" (16) The novel, p. 45.

"He stood looking at the rear of the departing train while the regret rippled over him with heartburn."

It is interesting to note what the researcher (HananAql) presented in her study of women in Noor's novel by Youssef Zaidan - where she described it as a novel about the Arab woman in the great prison)). As she reported: "Zidane in his trilogy: Mohal, Guantanamo and Noor. He goes through different kind of experimentation from what he had previously started in his previous works that were dominated by historical and mythological character, to provide philosophical and intellectual reading in the current reality of the Arab man or perhaps an illustration of his confusion, misery and feeling lost" (17) Al-Arab newspaper -22/10/2016

In *Mahal*, *Guantanamo*, *Noor*, there are no successive generations, and there is no extended period of time that we have to divide into stages,

In *Mahal*'s novel, it tells, in the language of the knowledgeable narrator, about the character of the hero (Muhammad) and the heroine (Noor) who represent the confused spirit of the Arab man in his youth.

This enables the reader to adopt the idea of being lost and confused in the period extending from the time of the novel in the early 1990s to the events of September 11, 2001. Here, the human connection to the place appears. (18) Al-Arab Newspaper / Researcher HananAqeel, Saturday 10/22/2016.

Mohal represents the human connection to place and loss.

In an interview with the writer conducted by the researcher HananAqeel, in which he referred to the high political tone in Mahal's novel, Guantanamo. To constitute a means of condemning the bitter Arab reality, politically, socially and intellectually.

Zidan clarifies in the conclusion of his speech that he seeks, through writing, to raise language and public awareness, and this is one of the manifestations of the Cultural Revolution that he seeks.

"I say my word and go as the early adopters did." Zaidan (19), *ibid*.

Among the narrative paradoxes created by the narrator is the return of the hero again to see the beloved who is about to leave her through a dramatic justification, as he remembered while at his work in Aswan that she forgot the wristwatch that her father gave to her, so he asks about the trip and he is told that the trip and the students are still in the city of Luxor) Then he quickly follows her to see the beloved with a moment of intense longing and eagerness. "His heart beat with joy when he saw Dr. Hedaya, on the left side, with Noor, next to her. He gave the wristwatch to its owner, and she thanked him with joy, with tearful eyes ... " (20) The novel, p. 57

Noor says: "Frankly, I don't know how I changed since I saw you, and everything in you attracted me to you, as if I were a piece of you that was removed ... " (21) The novel, p. 58

"He is the bird and the light of his safe nest" (22) p. 61

A press interview conducted by the researcher HananAqil with the novelist Youssef Zaidan in the issue of Saturday 22/10/2016, Al-Arab newspaper.

Entering into the character of the parallel hero in the novel "Mahal" represented by the hero's lover "Noor" shows an educated girl who lived her childhood in agony and oppression,

The scenes of the novel have spotted her since her mother died in a tragic accident "The Train Accident" and her father married another woman. Perhaps the Arab drama portrayed these scenes that represent the "stepmother", so she lived sad, oppressed, suffering from the pain of loss and absence.

She says: "When he asked her about her mother, a tinge of sadness rushed to her face, and she was distracted for a moment, and her eyes nearly teared up, then she told him stories: The late wife was originally from Mansoura and there my father saw her while he was training in the Mahalla al-Kubra company, and he loved her.

He married her and brought her to Alexandria, and they lived together for three years and ten months.

The day after tomorrow comes her anniversary, on the eighteenth day of January 1975, my mother died in a train accident ... I was three years old at the time, two years later, my father got married to "TantToha", who is a sharp-tempered woman who takes care of herself and does not care much to others" (23) the novel, p. 63.

My father's age is now approaching fifty-five, but he seems sad as someone who has reached seventy, whispering to her always that she reminds him of her mother, and that is why he is greatly afraid of her and worries. " (24) The novel, p. 63.

However, the biggest event in her life is the unjust desire of her stepmother, that she seeks to marry her early to a wealthy Libyan man, as Noor has always rejected this marriage. "His name is strange; MiftahMuftah Al-Mabrouk, but she calls it "Al-Zift" because he is sticky, and she does not love him or accept his gifts, because she does not want to marry a man who has exceeded forty, and he always confirms that he lives with his Libyan wife and describes her as ugliness and aggression. " (25) The novel, p. 64

The researcher believes that this serious concern in the imagination of our hero "Muhammad" about this adversary, the Libyan husband, made him insist on questions awaiting definitive answers from his girlfriend, "Noor", so he was reassured that his Libyan opponent wanted her but she did not want him.

Narrative events alternate in descriptive scenes expressed by the narrator in a poetic language that predicts a tremendous literary and cultural lexicon enjoyed by "Zidane" and countless luminous aesthetics that extended across the pages of the novel. This was evident when the hero "Muhammad" told his beloved Noor about his culture and creativity in saying poetry: "He told her that he used to write poetry and had verses about brown skin.

She rejoiced as she invited him to say it. He looked at the end of the sea, for a moment, and listened himself as he said in a deep, light voice:

I wanted as fate wanted ... so the moons of love came to dwell in it, for in the night I am a sign of the sun, and in the day a sign of a moon ... I wanted it as fate wanted ... (26) The novel, p. 82

Our hero is no longer able to separate the beloved, so he decided to leave her city, Alexandria, his argument for that to his family and friends in Aswan that he was going to obtain a tourist guide certificate in a specialized institute located in the city of Alexandria, and there, he was alone to stand at the places of the beloved that he visited and traveled with her to become The place is a symbol of love that reminds him of his beloved wherever he travels.

He says, "What is love? It is a divine gift that God gives to whomever he chooses among his servants, and gives him some of his lights ... " (27) The novel, p. 91

The researcher believes that the writer "Youssef Zaidan" came to have a poetic narrative language full of moments of Sufi abundance that he believed in from a young age, and his multiple readings in this field made

him a writer full of mystical language and vocabulary that was scattered across textual areas of this novel "Mahal". Here, the protagonist of the novel, according to the well-informed narrator, reviews the parents' opposition to his marriage to this Alexandrian girl - as he said - when his friend Hajj Bilal asked him, saying, Bilal to help him convince his father about the matter, because it is easier to convince him of that than to convince his mother who wants him to return to Omdurman so that he will remain under her wings, according to what he has always heard. (28) The novel, p. 89.

Our "hero" dared to meet the father of his beloved (Noor). He asked to marry her in a traditional and sacred manner, saying: "At the café on Al-Bayasa Square, he met her father, and he found no resistance or acceptance in him.

The man is good, he welcomed him and started asking about his work and his family, and whether he has an apartment, he answered as the situation permits, and confirmed that he will buy an apartment in Aswan next winter.

So the father, with resentment, said: Aswan.

Ok, can I bring my father and read Al-Fatiha?

The Fatihah is flexible, my son,

Go now and next year, we will see what happens (29), the novel, p. 92.

But our rebellious hero was overwhelmed by longing and could not wait for the customs and traditions in which he had long believed in previously, he buys the ring and agrees with his beloved on the family in a de facto situation, and imagines the upcoming meeting with his sweetheart after he puts her on a garment of love and holiness, and the moment of love came with sexual suggestion that linked Adam and Eve since ever: Noor grabbed his palm and inserted the ring into the left finger of the married couple, then extended her thin left hand to him while she was surrendering, then he inserted the other ring into her finger, so she immediately kissed her and tilted her head to his shoulder, and her chest fluttered with his arm, his jealousy of euphoria and emotion, tremors he did not know before, turned his head and drunk his sweat even though that this situation did not pass before him with human beings or Jinn, lovers are ever dreamers, and their dreams are obscured ... " (30) p. 95

The primitive rituals came to express the cohesion of the lovers and their union in a single existential destiny, as if the writer waved a social vision that at one time referred to a ritual in primitive marriage and ancient customs, so our writer is immersed in a human heritage to a large extent: "Noor was satisfied with the primitive ritual and extended her hand to him and cut in it a lightly a small wound, then press their hands so that their blood mixes in the veins ... " (31) The novel, p. 101

"clouds far away, pink trees surrounded by silk, and bright dreams washed with love, clear and rainy, and unearthly joy and abundant ..." (32) The novel, p. 102.

The descriptive scene created by the protagonist in a sexual image steeped in lust and cohesion represents the condition of man in his first creation, searching for his salvation and his connection with the "beloved" woman, lost in the fertile land whose source is women in different ages and civilizations, a symbol of fertility and generosity.

Zidane's eye observes a descriptive scene, very wonderful and perfect for a state of eternal love that was evident in the universe, saying:

"After we became dizzy with feelings, the upper bound was removed from her, and her breasts fell and revolted, his eyes lost in her breasts and his patience collapsed, she threw her dress from her, lost her corners with the stings of flames, and the bed sheets were broken beneath them. They fell to the ground and became for them a bed and mats, and a sea threatening to drown, so her heart would release gasps when the embrace intensified"(33) The novel 113

The image of the traitorous woman: "treason."

Zaidan insists in his novel "Mahal" to stand at the secrets of the human soul and the circumstances and justifications that came to the image of the woman traitorous to herself, her family, her community and her faith. However, the justification for betrayal, as Zaidan believes, does not give the woman the right to this sin that sticks to her throughout her life. Treason denotes a broken family, lost children and a lost husband, and this belief, as the researcher sees, has its honorific doctrinal significance, which is represented in the betrayal of the stepmother (Noor's father) to her husband with her lover, the Libyan intelligence officer who lured her with wealth and money and who remained under his control to carry out his orders to pressure Noor's father to agree. On her marriage to him.

But Noor was not able to leave her house daily, as she had done in previous years, and her father would no longer support her in front of his wife, who is affiliated with the Libyan agent, and they conspired against her after she exposed them and their secret immorality was revealed.

Noor cannot confront and is unable to disclose what she saw. Compassion for her poor father who surrendered to his defeat, in front of his cheap wife, and the family's unfaithful friend. (34) The novel, p. 116.

The other scene was evident in 1997, which the hero calls a year of disasters and an inauspicious year, where the betrayal of the wife of his friend Sohail, who is a tourist guide who works with him in Aswan, and they have a

good friendship with her cousin, the baker, who learned this from his first wife, saying: "His first wife is the same. For the thirty years, she insinuated throughout the past days about nefarious things that refer to his second wife, who is a few years younger than her, Sohail was upset at her insinuation and vague words, and he hit her, and she spoke out in his face that his other wife was immoral. The younger wife meets her cousin, "Atiya" the baker, secretly, in the room in which he lives alone in Aswan" (35) p. 119. He revealed his secret to his close friend, the protagonist of the novel (Muhammad), who watched it, and became sure of the authenticity of the news, and the result was tragic. Sohail returned to a life of loss and advent with foreign tourists.

"Two days later, people here whispered that Sohail's traitorous ex-wife had disappeared, some of them said that she fled to Cairo with the baker, but many believe that her family killed her and buried her behind the far eastern hills." (36) The novel, p. 122.

The hero "Muhammad" comments on this tragic and disgraceful story, saying: "The man in this matter is not the woman, why is the crime greater when it is committed by the woman, and it becomes smaller when the man commits it, so the correct view is that both of them leave in the other guilt and disobedience." (37) The novel, p. 122.

The ill-fated year seemed justified to our hero, Sohail, his friend, lost and confused. The State Security officer tells him that his work permit has expired and that he must leave for his country, Sudan, and his lover does not answer his phone and calls for a long time, and he does not know anything about her, and he must implement the state order So he goes quickly to his family in Sudan.

So he wrote poetry saying: Is this torment a sin, unintentionally it has become, O Lord, it is a choice, O Lord, it has become worse and blackened as the night and day, and patience is defeated in me, and the wall collapses.

The novel takes us to an accelerated rhythm through a series of events that are not without jumps in time, so our hero Muhammad lives for a period of time in the arms of his family in Sudan and invites his sad friend Sohail to live with him there, hoping that he may emerge from the crisis of betrayal that he suffered from, and convince him to travel to inquire about the matter of his beloved (Noor), about whom nothing is known and her news has been cut off, so he goes to Alexandria by plane because he is Sudanese and the State Security has finished his work permit in Aswan, and they are chasing him and asking about him, and the family sympathized with him after they saw his poor condition to lose his lost love, so they convinced him to travel to her by air as a traveler Comes from another country.

This was achieved and he went down to Alexandria and met her friend Amal, who was surprised by the fact that his girlfriend was forced to marry the Libyan intelligence officer in a dramatic way, and her father was exposed to severe liver disease while he was poor. "As we mentioned," came the power of money that Zaidan always referred to in This novel, forcing the beloved to marry this man who cannot even hear his name, so he took care of her father's treatment and took her home and she had a child from him, and to the great surprise he made sure that this child was his daughter, so he became in a state of shock and extreme sadness, and he was unable to meet the beloved where her friend Amal convinced him that she was in a state of extreme sadness, if you looked at her, you would not know her.

A week after their last meeting, Noor married a Libyan man and gave birth to a baby girl who is now nine months old. She was compelled because her father had suffered kidney failure two months earlier, so the Libyan man pledged to treat him ... " (38) The novel, p. 143

-Pleas Amal, I need to see Noor.

-Pleas, just leave her alone she is suffering already, Noor has gone.

The burdens descended upon him in his loneliness, so that he did not rise from his position to ward off the gusts of rain that suddenly rained down ... (39) The novel, p. 143

In this point, events take us to his escape from his bitter reality and the diligence of his family and friends, and they found work for him in the UAE, so our hero stands at amazing textual paradoxes, and the narrator describes the Emirati cities and compares them with Sharjah, Fujairah and Dubai,

"With the diligence of his mother and the help of his family and neighbors, many attempts were made until they found a job for him in the distant Gulf countries ..." (40) The novel, p. 145.

There he meets the Syrian expatriate, Fawaz, his manager at work, and they have a good relationship.

The pain of separation continued to insist on our hero in his exile, representing the vision of our beloved in his solution and his journey "I am nothing but a bewildered spirit that ranges between places, or have I become on the contrary, a body the soul has disappeared from after the parting of Noor ..." the novel, p. 150

Time takes us to the hero's journey to Bukhari with the beginning of the year 2000, the new millennium "The year is about to end, and people around are preparing to welcome what they call the new millennium ..." (41) Novel 153.

Wife's picture

Another leap of time since the beginning of the second new millennium, his friend at work, the Syrian expatriate, "Fawaz", takes him to his home and introduces him to his family in Uzbekistan, where the new dairy factory will be established there and the blessing of the Emirati wealthy Sheikh Khalifa, the owner of the factory, so that the hero works in this new factory, and takes over the management there. The drama comes in

the events where his friend "Fawaz" proposes to him the idea of marrying an Uzbek Muslim girl. This is "Mahira", the daughter of Fawaz's wife. She was raised in his house on good morals, religiosity and respect. She was nineteen years old. This surprise came to our hero in the novel. As it coincided with his loneliness and sadness in these distant, harsh conditions, perhaps comforting his unity and his loss.

Then he immediately entered to pray in which the sky was asked if it was right for him to marry a good, calm, white Uzbek, and he almost went out from the threshold of the mosque, until he decided in his heart that the girl was suitable for him, and he relaxed himself to the idea of marriage, so he asked Alisher to take him back to Fawwaz. 42) Novel, p. 186

"He did not know that Mahira is so beautiful..,Mahira has fallen from heaven."

The researcher thinks that the image of the girl, the peaceful, calm, obedient wife has drawn its shadows on the soul and conscience of our hero.

The sanctity of the husband, the feeling of societal masculinity, was evident in this simple woman who was brought up in a traditional Islamic education that obeying a husband is a matter of obedience to God Almighty.

The novel ends on an open vision that allows the recipient to interpret events as he wishes. Our hero is driven and falls into the hands of terrorists and is imprisoned where there is no return, and his girl is waiting for his return, and his first boy does not know anything about him.

"And I think that they took him to America to deposit him in one of its prisons, but he was wrong in his belief ... This land on which he landed is not America, its Cuba, and he will not be imprisoned in the next seven years in a regular prison, but he will remain a prisoner in a terrible prison run secretly by the American army, its name is Guantanamo." (43) The novel, p. 244

The researcher believes that the image of the beloved woman in this novel came as a resistance to the bitter reality in which she is living and declared a state of rebellion. The heroine of the novel, Noor, succumbed to her circumstances at first, but she returned and gathered her strength with her first help and support.

However, the image of the Arab woman on the waiting list and fear of the unknown was represented by the character of the second wife, "Mahira", who remained trapped in this waiting and submissive soul.

The researcher (ZulfaShahrou) believes that Zaidan excelled in describing the lives of simple people in all its details, feelings, life and economic concerns, and the absence of certainty in the future, which turned many of them into religious people in search of life satisfaction and hope for paradise.

(44))

Margins:

- 1- Youssef Zaidan's novels, respectively: the novel "Mahal: 2012, Guantanamo 2014, Noor 2016."
- 2- Youssef Zaidan and his triple: an analytical study, India Film Magazine (electronic magazine) Muhammad Shafi` Al-Zaman, fourth year, first issue (January - March 2019)
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